

FEATURES OF AN INDIVIDUALIZED APPROACH IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES USING BOXING EXERCISES FOR PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article examines the features of an individualized approach in physical education classes incorporating boxing exercises and elements. Special attention is given to the necessity of adapting training to the individual characteristics of students, as active physical activity positively contributes to their personal and physical development. The study also highlights the role of boxing and its exercises as an effective tool for conducting physical education sessions.

Keywords: physical education, sport, boxing, students, individualized approach, training sessions.

Introduction. Today, physical education plays a vital role in the lives of university students. A healthy lifestyle involves regular physical activity, adherence to specific forms of exercise, and maintaining a structured daily routine.

Physical training helps develop the motor skills necessary not only for daily life but also for future professional activities. The development of these skills should be based on the principles of physical education while taking into account the individual characteristics of students. Achieving this requires thorough testing and the application of appropriate methods and training tools. It is well known that exercises that do not match a student's individual capabilities can lead to mental fatigue, reducing the effectiveness of physical education and overall performance [6].

An individualized approach in physical education classes is closely linked to the methodology of its implementation. Physical education instructors should plan their work taking into account students' age, body type, and personal characteristics. The goal is to foster an environment in which acquiring knowledge, skills, and abilities becomes both essential and enjoyable, providing students with a sense of satisfaction and intrinsic motivation.

Research Aim. The aim of this study is to explore ways to meet university students' physical needs and help them achieve high levels of physical and technical fitness through individualized training sessions.

According to some specialists, every student possesses a unique combination of physical abilities and individual traits. By taking these into account, it becomes possible to foster the development of a well-rounded personality [1].

Key motivational factors include health status, physical development, correction of certain body deficiencies, enhancement of physical abilities, acquisition of essential skills, psychological and physical readiness for a chosen profession, and the attainment of desired athletic outcomes.

Each physical education instructor has their own teaching style, yet all share a sensitive and attentive approach to their students, applying individualized methods for each, which is crucial for achieving successful outcomes. The teacher's personality plays a significant role in this process. Their pedagogical skill, combined with personal qualities, shapes students' responses to both the instructor and the subjects being taught, making the learning experience unique and effective.

A positive relationship with physical education instructors fosters a greater interest in physical activity among many university students. To develop and sustain this interest, it is necessary to [5]:

1. stimulate students' curiosity;
2. enhance the quality of learning by teaching students to approach the educational process seriously and work diligently, rather than treating it as mere entertainment;
3. organize students' self-directed learning in a way that enables them, upon leaving the university, to find methods and resources to maintain their physical fitness independently.

The individualized approach allows university instructors to identify students' abilities and skills in specific sports. Applying this approach in the educational process enables teachers to take into account these and other individual characteristics, positively influencing the learning process and fostering student interest.

To implement an individualized approach effectively, instructors must continuously observe their students and understand their personal traits. For example, a student with an unstable or highly excitable nervous system may absorb material inconsistently during classes, while calmer students tend to assimilate information at a relatively steady and consistent pace.

In universities, this issue requires significant attention due to the annual decline in students' health and physical fitness levels. For example, at the Tashkent branch of A.I. Herzen Russian State Pedagogical University, this problem is addressed by

enhancing the effectiveness of the “Physical Education” course through the integration of exercises and elements from various sports during training sessions.

An individualized approach helps to prolong the benefits of training while enabling students to quickly restore their physical condition. Depending on a student’s health status, other types of exercises may also be considered to develop their physical qualities. These qualities are closely linked to the student’s motor skills. Physical attributes reflect the stable functional capacities of the body, both innate and acquired, and the coordinated interaction of organs ensures an adequate level of overall functional performance.

An individualized approach in physical education and sports helps create conditions in which students can derive satisfaction from applying their abilities and skills. Training sessions for all student groups should be conducted with balanced physical loads and a moderate pace. Exercises are designed to progressively increase demands on students while taking into account medical contraindications [2].

At the Tashkent branch of A.I. Herzen Russian State Pedagogical University, physical education specialists have developed a questionnaire for students. This survey is conducted to gather information about the physical condition of each student (see Table 1).

Table-1
A questionnaire for student

A questionnaire for student	
Date of Completion	_____
Full Name	_____
Group	_____
Date of Birth	_____
Gender	_____
Nutrition Habits	_____
Medical History (Illnesses, Surgeries, Injuries)	_____

Previous Sports Experience	_____
Weight	_____
Height	_____
Alcohol and Tobacco Use	_____
Preferred Sports Activities	_____

By studying and analyzing the information collected through the student questionnaire, instructors can identify more effective approaches in physical education and sports, taking into account factors such as gender, nutrition habits, medical conditions, injuries, surgeries, unhealthy habits, weight, height, and other individual characteristics.

Depending on each student’s health profile – such as overweight, respiratory or cardiac issues – the instructor develops a personalized training program tailored to their specific needs.

It is also important to obtain accurate information from students regarding their alcohol and tobacco consumption, including the amount and frequency. Additionally, students’ work and life conditions should be considered, as stress outside the university can significantly affect their well-being.

Another critical factor is the student’s medical history. Instructors should inquire about the current health status, including any pain or discomfort. A tailored physical education and sports program for each student can then effectively support their overall development.

According to researchers [7], a promising, accessible, and effective way to improve physical condition is the integration of physical education as a key component of a healthy lifestyle. Physical training is an essential part of education, aimed at strengthening students’ health. However, some educational programs fail to deliver the desired results. This raises the question of how to enhance students’ physical condition and improve their overall fitness.

To address this issue, physical education instructors at the Tashkent branch of A.I. Herzen Russian State Pedagogical University employ exercises and elements

from various sports, such as boxing, in both group sessions and individualized training.

Since boxing is an effective means of comprehensive physical development, exercises from this contact sport help strengthen the musculoskeletal system and develop qualities such as speed, strength-speed abilities, power, accuracy, and coordination of movements, while also activating vital bodily functions [8].

The positive impact of boxing on the development of motor and mental functions, as well as the cultivation of moral and volitional qualities, allows it to be regarded not only as a sport but also as a powerful tool for physical education and the personal development of students.

Through general physical training, students develop various physical abilities, including overall endurance, speed, speed-strength qualities, coordination, and more. The combination of general physical preparation and boxing exercises contributes to improved health and enhances the functioning of the students' bodies. Students gain a better understanding of training loads, adapt more quickly, and achieve higher levels of athletic performance. Furthermore, they acquire technical skills more effectively. Volitional qualities are also strengthened, as training with boxing exercises helps students overcome challenges, promotes psychological resilience, and supports the long-term maintenance of physical fitness. Overall, this leads to a significant improvement in performance dynamics [3].

Individualized training using boxing exercises is effective because, regardless of a student's previous experience with boxing, such sessions allow them to achieve desired results in a relatively short period. Moreover, an individualized approach reduces the risk of injury, taking into account the current physical condition of university students.

Individual training sessions incorporating boxing elements offer several advantages:

1. Students can feel more comfortable and fully realize their hidden potential;
2. Precision and targeted skills, defensive techniques, and proper boxing techniques are more effectively developed;
3. They allow students to develop their own individual fighting style.

Experts in boxing theory and methodology recommend the following exercises to develop excellent movement coordination, punching power, optimal breathing, and a healthy cardiovascular system [4]:

1. Specialized boxing stretching exercises – these stretches target the muscles of the arms, legs, and back, reducing the risk of injury. They also improve blood circulation and increase the range of motion.

2. Jump rope exercises – jumping rope warms up the entire body and significantly reduces the risk of injury. It also helps develop endurance and address excess weight. During rope exercises, attention should be paid to breathing and maintaining a relaxed posture.

3. Shadowboxing – this fundamental boxing exercise is aimed at practicing and reinforcing proper movement mechanics. Shadowboxing allows students to work on both offensive and defensive movements. Beginners are advised to follow structured rounds, such as practicing straight punches while moving forward, hooks after ducking, and punches while retreating, etc.

4. Heavy bag training – these exercises are designed to develop speed, speed-strength qualities, movement coordination, and accuracy. Students should start with slow straight punches, gradually increasing the pace, and then progress to combinations of straight and hook punches. Maintaining rhythm and proper breathing is essential.

5. Focus mitt training – suitable for both beginners and students with more than a year of boxing experience. This training helps reinforce boxing techniques, learn and practice tactical movements, improve physical endurance, develop precise and coordinated motions, train the correct distribution of muscular force, and practice relaxation when necessary.

6. Weighted exercises – these exercises help students perfect their technique and build significant endurance. Since the hands are the primary tools of a boxer, using weighted implements allows students to refine their punches even when performing without added weight.

7. Mirror training – this method helps improve boxing technique and transforms learned skills into refined maneuvers. Additionally, these exercises enhance the mobility of all arm muscles and strengthen punches executed in various combinations.

Conclusion. A student-centered approach in higher education means that students can choose the physical education methods offered by the instructor. This approach in university physical education and sports training allows students to view personal health, personality development, and individuality as the foundation for self-realization.

Furthermore, a structured training program with an individualized approach, incorporating boxing exercises and elements, promotes active engagement of students in this dynamic sport. Boxing helps develop essential qualities such as determination, strength, willpower, and courage. Practicing sequential techniques ensures that sessions remain engaging and emotionally stimulating, while allowing the selection of effective exercises with varying degrees of novelty and difficulty.

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